

Research Article

A mechanical blender for homogenization of the pulps of guava

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ABSTRACT

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Conventional juices settle regardless of the production method used. In order to achieve a complete homogenization, it often requires chemical additives. In a world increasingly conscious of its food consumption, we expect to explore a new way of producing homogeneous juice, without additives, by using a mechanical mixer and refine it later with one of the new physical processes. Applied to guava pulp, the influence of the water / guava ratio at constant volume is an important factor through which several parameters were monitored. To achieve this, the quantification of the mechanical power of the mill allowed us to measure the actual energy required to obtain a product having a particle size distribution determined. Thus the Reynolds number and the shear rate of the grinder with respect to the volume, the torque of the mill and the Reynolds number based on the rate were monitored. After having determined the volume range corresponding to the optimum grinding, particle size distribution at different positions of the mill has been mastered by the influence of dilution at constant volume.

Keywords:

homogenization, guava, blender, mechanical power, shear rate.

INTRODUCTION

Technological requirements, improving facilities and food are on constants developments. Guava (*Psidium guajava L.*) can serve as a sources of foreign exchange to countries' producers (Martine, 2003; Jamin et al., 2003). This fruit is rich in polysaccharides and pectin substance that cause problems at the processing level of the finished product. Thus we encounter problems of settling juice to the radius and at high viscosity due to pectin. To solve the viscosity problem, we proceed by an enzymatic depectinisation of guava pulp (Kengni, 2000) or by liquefaction of pectin's cell wall (Legentil, 1996; Bekhouche, 2006). The previous methods do not solve the problem of particle size. The disadvantages associated with the biochemical method by introducing a foreign product, that is, the synthetic enzymes (commercial enzymes; product synthesis) are the risks of change in taste and color (Sale and Hamilton, 1967; Rzedowski 1972, Durand et al., 1982, Grahl and Markl, 1996; Barbosa-Canovas et al., 1998; Jeantet et al., 1999; Errendilek et al., 2000, Cheng et al., 2007). An alternative to the enzymatic treatment is the use of new physical process to provide a refining phase to the production of guava juice. In the transformation of guava juice to our knowledge, there is limited information on the output power of grinding and particle size of mash to obtain a good grinding which is an essential operation in juice production. It can condition the quality of the finished product. Because we want to study the homogenization of guava juice by new physical process and in the literature, to our knowledge no information is given on the particle size obtained after grinding, it is necessary to analyze the homogenization of guava pulp by a grinder. This work aims to determine the mechanical power of stirring the mill corresponding to a precise volume and to measure the size of the particles formed after grinding. For this, we will present the material and methods which helped us to achieve the above objectives, and then we will discuss the results in order to offer some perspectives.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

To avoid variations related to fruit sources as part of this work, the type of guava used as *Psidium guajava L.*, pink varieties, come from a single plantation not far from the University of Ngaoundéré, Adamawa Region, Cameroon. To achieve the above objective, the present work is devoted to the influence of ratio guava / water on the particle size of raw juice.

- $g = (n_0 - n) / n_0$,
- $P_a = VI \cos\phi$,
- $P_{cts} = P_{fs} + P_m$
- $P_{js} = R_s \cdot I^2$ and,
- $P_{tr} = P_a - R_s \cdot I^2 - 1/2 P_{cts}$,
- $P_{jr} = g \cdot P_{tr}$,
- $\Sigma \text{ Losses} = P_{js} + P_{jr} + P_{ct}$,
- $P_u = P_a - \Sigma \text{ losses} = 2\pi n T_u$,

Guavas are sorted and washed, crushed in a blender named Windsor Blender, Model No. 1030, 230 V / 400 W. Measuring the power absorbed by our grinder is given by a power meter Chauvin Arnoux CA 405.

We selected a digital tachometer 01-2015, NF5601 of AOIP for measuring the rotation speed of the motor shaft of the blender. Finally, the size distribution of our pulp is done through the Malvern Instruments Master sizer S. MSX64, France. We added to this list of equipment a HACH turbidimeter, Model Ratio / XR HACH Company USA. It allows monitoring the turbidity, a parameter used to measure the disorder in midst.

Measurement of particle size

To determine the particle diameter, particle size will be performed by a laser diffraction particle sizer, Malvern Master sizer, S. MSX64 Malvern Instruments, France.

PH measurement

An electrode (TACUSSEL) is introduced in the solution which the pH is to be determined. This is obtained by direct reading on the dashboard of the pH meter.

Measurement of the mechanical energy of the grinder by the separated loss method.

Our grinder incorporates a single-phase induction motor. Determining the output power for this case cannot be done by the direct method. Therefore, we used the method of separated losses. To measure the rotation speed of the tree, we conducted an extension of the rotor shaft. The separated loss method requires:

- Measurement of the power absorbed in the atmosphere at different speeds,
- Measurement of the load power demand at different speeds in order to calculate the slip,
- Measurement of the resistance of winding at heat.
- And we calculate the Joule losses in the stator, the rotor and the constant losses (Lucas and Charrault, 1987; Dalmaso, 1987; Garot, 1991; Boye, 1995; Wozniak, 2004).

With all these tests, we could calculate the power output.

The main experimental results are summarized in Tables 1, 2 and 3 in the measured and calculated quantities using the following relations:

- $\eta = P_u / P_a$ (Lucas et al., 1987; Garot, 1991; Boye, 1995; Wozniak, 2004),
- $f = 2\pi n / 60$,
- $Re = \rho D^2 f / \mu$,
- $G^2 = P_u / (V\rho^2)$ (Chhabra and Richardson, 1999).

Based on the data obtained from these relationships, multiple graphs can be obtained like the output grinding torque and of the Reynolds number based on the speed of blades, the Reynolds number, and shear rate G (s^{-1} or Hz) with respect to volume.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To study the influence of guava / water ratio on the size of the pulp, tests were carried out at different

dilutions and different positions of the grinder. The results obtained are illustrated respectively by figure 1-6 and 7 to 10 for grinding at different positions (1, 2 and 3):

- With water and without dilution
 - With dilutions 50, 150 and 250 ml of tap water (pH: 6.98; Turbidity: 2 NTU).
 - At constant volume of 750 ml and 1500 ml.
- Tables 1, 2 and 3 stand the experimental results for the different positions of the grinder.

Table 1: Data table from different experimental measurements of blender (Windsor Blender) for position 1

<i>Test at position 1</i>											
Volume (ml)	Average voltage (V)	Intensity, I (A)	Vaccum power, P ₀ (W)	Consumption power, P _a (W)	Resistance, R (Ω)	Joules losses at the stator, P _{js} (W)	Transmitted power, P _{tr} (W)	Joules losses at the rotor, P _{jr} (W)	Sum of losses, ΣP(W)	Output power, P _u (W)	Output torque, T _u (N.m)
250	223.850	0.850	188.400	213.930	26.750	19.327	100.403	0162	207.889	6.041	0.00006
500	222.900	0.985	188.400	237.640	26.750	25.954	117.486	0.456	214.810	22.830	0.00024
750	224.450	1.225	188.400	279.320	26.750	40.142	144.978	1.858	230.400	48.920	0.00051
1000	223.000	1.415	188.400	315.000	26.750	53.560	167.240	4.454	246.414	68.586	0.00073
1250	223.300	1.470	188.400	329.010	26.750	57.804	177.006	6.897	253.101	75.909	0.00081
1500	223.500	1.555	188.400	342.570	26.750	64.682	183.688	10.468	263.551	79.019	0.00086

Table 1: Data table from different experimental measurements of blender (Windsor Blender) for position 1(continued)

Volume (ml)	Load speed, n ₀ (Rev / min)	Average speed, n (Rev / min)	Slip, n _r (%)	Frequency, f (s ⁻¹)	Output power, P _u (W)	Shear rate, G (s ⁻¹ or Hz)	Reynolds number
250	15450.000	15425.000	0.162	1614.483	6.041	4915.551	6206073.933
500	15450.000	15390.000	0.388	1610.820	22.830	6757.251	6191992.080
750	15450.000	15252.000	1.282	1596.376	48.920	8076.328	6136469.344
1000	15450.000	15038.500	2.663	1574.030	68.586	8281.675	6050570.039
1250	15450.000	14848.000	3.896	1554.091	75.909	7792.766	5973924.523
1500	15450.000	14569.500	5.699	1524.941	79.019	7258.072	5861873.204

Table 2: Data table from different experimental measurements of blender (Windsor Blender) for position 2

<i>Test at position 2</i>											
Volume (ml)	Average voltage (V)	Intensity, I (A)	Vaccum power, P ₀ (W)	Consumption power, P _a (W)	Resistance, R (Ω)	Joules losses at the stator, P _{js} (W)	Transmitted power, P _{tr} (W)	Joules losses at the rotor, P _{jr} (W)	Sum of losses, ΣP(W)	Output power, P _u (W)	Output torque, T _u (N.m)
250	226.550	0.850	206.900	240.518	25.750	18.582	118.486	7.359	232.841	7.677	0.00008
500	225.550	0.901	206.900	263.820	25.750	20.904	139.466	8.975	236.779	27.041	0.00028
750	225.000	0.896	206.900	305.090	25.750	20.673	180.967	13.350	240.923	64.167	0.00066
1000	224.150	0.878	206.900	328.310	25.750	19.850	205.010	18.026	244.776	83.534	0.00087
1250	224.500	0.957	206.900	344.140	25.750	23.583	217.107	21.531	252.014	92.126	0.00098
1500	225.550	1.027	206.900	356.000	25.750	27.133	225.417	26.675	260.708	95.292	0.00103

Table 2: Data table from different experimental measurements of blender (Windsor Blender) for position 2(continued)

Volume (ml)	Load speed, n ₀ (Rev / min)	Average speed, n (Rev / min)	Slip, n _r (%)	Frequency, f (s ⁻¹)	Output power, P _u (W)	Shear rate, G (s ⁻¹ or Hz)	Reynolds number
250	16673.000	15637.500	6.211	1636.725	7.677	5541.407	6291570.900
500	16673.000	15600.000	6.436	1632.800	27.041	7354.007	6276483.200
750	16673.000	15443.000	7.377	1616.367	64.167	9249.660	6213316.029
1000	16673.000	15207.000	8.793	1591.666	83.534	9139.690	6118364.104
1250	16673.000	15019.500	9.917	1572.041	92.126	8584.912	6042925.604
1500	16673.000	14700.000	11.834	1538.600	95.292	7970.63	5914378.400

Table 3: Data table from different experimental measurements of blender (Windsor Blender) for position 3

<i>Test at position 3</i>											
Volume (ml)	Average voltage (V)	Intensity, I (A)	Vaccum power, P ₀ (W)	Consumption power, P _a (W)	Resistance, R (Ω)	Joules losses at the stator, P _{js} (W)	Transmitted power, P _{tr} (W)	Joules losses at the rotor, P _{jr} (W)	Sum of losses, ΣP(W)	Output power, P _u (W)	Output torque, T _u (N.m)
250	226.20	0.84	179.05	218.33	26.10	18.22	110.58	11.60	208.87	9.46	0.0001
500	222.85	0.87	179.05	248.30	26.10	19.53	139.25	14.86	213.43	34.87	0.0004
750	224.50	0.89	179.05	297.8	26.10	20.51	187.04	21.27	220.84	76.25	0.0008
1000	223.00	0.87	179.05	325.46	26.10	19.66	216.27	27.33	226.04	99.42	0.0010
1250	225.30	0.95	179.05	344.74	26.10	23.48	231.74	31.97	234.50	110.24	0.0012
1500	224.70	1.03	179.05	362.40	26.10	27.47	245.40	38.37	244.90	117.50	0.0013

Table 3: Data table from different experimental measurements of blender (Windsor Blender) for position 3(continued)

Volume (ml)	Load speed, n ₀ (Rev / min)	Average speed, n (Rev / min)	Slip, n _r (%)	Frequency, f (s ⁻¹)	Output power, P _u (W)	Shear rate, G (s ⁻¹ or Hz)	Reynolds number
250	17650.00	15798	10.49	1653.52	9.46	6150.207	6356146.26
500	17650.00	15767	10.67	1650.28	34.87	8350.727	6343673.76
750	17650.00	15642.5	11.37	1637.25	76.25	10082.685	6293582.59
1000	17650.00	15420	12.63	1613.96	99.42	9971.183	6204062.24
1250	17650.00	15215	13.80	1592.50	110.24	9391.074	6121582.81
1500	17650.00	14890	15.64	1558.49	117.50	8850.713	5990822.75

Figure 1: Volume based on the speed of the blades

Figure 2: Reynolds number based on volume

It can be seen through the curves that the speed of the blades and the Reynolds number based on the volume at different positions, has two zones namely a

nonlinear region and a linear region. The first is between 250 and 750 ml and the second between 750 and 1250 ml.

Figure 3: Shear rate based on the volume

It appears that at volumes between 750 and 1000 ml of the velocity gradient graph, we are thus in the area of optimal parameters sought. The profiles of the

velocity gradient as a function of volume are similar for the different positions of our grinder.

Figure 4: Output grinding torque and Reynolds number based on the speed of the blades. The graph of the output grinding torque and Reynolds number as a function of the speed of blades has a parabolic branch whose intersection with the curve of the Reynolds number as a function of speed presents a nominal point. In our context, this intersection corresponds to the optimum product to put in the blender for a power output between 48.920 W and 68.586 W (see Table 1)

Figure 5: Output grinding torque and Reynolds number based on the speed of the blades

The graph of output grinding torque and Reynolds number as a function of the speed of the blades has a parabolic branch whose intersection with the curve of the Reynolds number based on the speed presents a

nominal point. In our context, this intersection corresponds to the optimum product to put in the blender with a power between 64.167 and 83.534 (see Table 2).

Figure 6: Output grinding torque and Reynolds number based on the speed of the blades

Graphs of output grinding torque and Reynolds number based on the speed of the blades have the same profile at different positions of the blender and show an intersection point around 15,400 Rev / min for a torque of $8.6 \cdot 10^{-4}$ Nm and a Reynolds number of

$6.24 \cdot 10^6$. The following graphs represent the particles sizes obtained after grinding at different dilutions

Figure 7: Grinding at different positions of 750 g of undiluted guava

Figure 8 : Grinding at different positions of 700 g of guava with addition of 50 ml of water

Figure 9 : Grinding at different positions of 600 g of guava with addition of 150 ml of water

Figure 10: Grinding at different positions of 500 g of guava with addition of 250 ml of water

The following table summarizes the sizes of our particles obtained after grinding for figures 7, 8, 9 and 10.

Table 4 : Particle size at different position

Guava mass (g)	water mass (g)	Grinding size (μm) at each position		
		Position 1	Position 2	Position 3
750	0	823.903	276.099	285.421
700	50	867.527	282.177	288.313
600	150	883.443	282.505	289.101
500	250	882.514	282.363	287.412

From these graphs, it appears that the size distributions of our pulps have a shoulder, proofs that they are not homogeneous.

Table 5: Tests for pH and turbidity of guava pulp at position 1

Mass of Guava, m_g (g)	mass of water, m_e (g)	Total mass, m_T (ml)	pH	Turbidity, T (NTU)	Dry Matter, MS (%)
750	0	750	4.01 \pm 0.01	19660.00 \pm 8.05	26.81
700	50	750	4.04 \pm 0.01	18660.00 \pm 7.07	25.02
600	150	750	4.08 \pm 0.02	17438.50 \pm 8.13	21.45
500	250	750	4.04 \pm 0.01	16960.00 \pm 7.07	17.87

Table 6: Tests for pH and turbidity of guava pulp at position 2

Guava mass, m_g (g)	Mass of water, m_e (g)	Total mass, m_T (ml)	pH	Turbidity, T (NTU)	Dry matter, MS (%)
750	0	750	4.01 \pm 0.01	19550.00 \pm 7.07	26.81
700	50	750	4.01 \pm 0.02	18660.00 \pm 7.07	25.02
600	150	750	4.01 \pm 0.01	17438.50 \pm 8.13	21.45
500	250	750	4.00 \pm 0.00	16851.00 \pm 6.36	17.87

Table 7: Tests for pH and turbidity of guava pulp at position 3

Guava mass, m_g (g)	Water mass, m_e (g)	Total mass, m_T (ml)	pH	Turbidity, T (NTU)	Dry matter, MS (%)
750	0	750	4.01 \pm 0.03	19450.00 \pm 7.07	26.81
700	50	750	4.02 \pm 0.02	18910.00 \pm 7.07	25.02
600	150	750	4.01 \pm 0.03	18855.00 \pm 3.54	21.45
500	250	750	4.01 \pm 0.00	16645.00 \pm 3.54	17.87

This table shows that:

- Dilution does not affect the size distribution of guava pulp;
- The pulp size decreases as the grinder speed increases;
- At positions 2 and 3 of the grinder we have similar particle size distributions.

This is because guava is very rich in water (74 to 88%) (Martine, 2003), the addition of water in the grinder does not alter the size distribution and thus does not allow the destruction of cells but instead

favors fluidization of the mixture. The velocity gradient is the cause of the observed distribution. The velocity gradients of positions 2 and 3 are identical and higher than that from position 1. However, grinding has required less time with the increase of the amount of water.

Measurements at different positions of our grinder in turbidity and pH in Tables 5, 6 and 7 were made at different times for the mash obtained without dilution and with dilutions at constant volume of 750 ml and 1000 ml. Mash samples taken for turbidity and pH measurements were taken in the middle of the test tube.

CONCLUSION

From the graphs of output grinding torque as function of speed, the Reynolds number based on velocity and velocity gradient based on volume, we were able to choose the area of unrest. From the graph of the velocity gradient as a function of volume, we have chosen the volume corresponding to the maximal effects of shear, indicated by the velocity gradient. The addition of water during the grinding does not reduce the particle size. The use of mechanical blender allows obtaining particle size at positions 1, 2 and 3 are respectively (823.903 μm , 276.099 μm and 285.421 μm) greater than 50 μm . In order to further reduce size and eliminate the shoulders obtained after the grinding stage of pulp for a homogeneous particle size distribution and less than 50 μm , we believe in studying the impact of ultrasound on the homogenization of guava juices.

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